

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

DMP Writing Made Easy: A Hands-on Workshop for Chemists

Ann-Christin Andres & Fabian Fink | 21.01.2026

Notes:

- *Welcome to the workshop DMP Writing Made Easy: A Hands-on Workshop for Chemists.*

Further information

- Wait 1-2 minutes for participants to join.

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Introduction

2

Notes:

- *In the beginning, we would like to start with a short introduction on us, our project, and the topic of data management in general.*

Further information:

- -

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Introduction

Organisational aspects

3

Notes:

- *But first, let's discuss the organisational aspects of today's workshop.*

Further information:

- -

Workshop rules

- Zoom
 - Mute your microphone if you are not speaking.
 - Turn your camera on 😊.
 - Raise your hand if you would like to say anything.
 - Raise your hand if you have any questions or write them in the chat. We will take care of your request immediately.
- Breakout rooms
 - Unmute your microphone.
 - After the scheduled time, leave the room and return to main room.
 - Or wait, you will be automatically redirected to the main room.

Notes:

- *Some words about our workshop rules...*
- *... and please turn on your cameras, this is an interactive workshop and it is much nicer to see a few faces than talking to a black screen.*
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- This slide is only important for online workshops, skip it if you are running an on-site workshop.
- By now most people are familiar with online conference tools like Zoom or Webex, but you should still go through the basic functions (camera, microphone, raise hand and chat).
- Actively ask the participants to turn on their cameras.

Time schedule

Time	Topic
09:00 - 09:30	Welcome, introduction to NFDI4Chem, and DMP basics
09:30 - 10:40	DMP Writing: Section 1 & 2
10:40 - 10:50	Coffee break
10:50 - 12:10	DMP Writing: Section 3 & 4
12:10 - 13:10	Lunch break
13:10 - 14:30	DMP Writing: Section 5 & 6
14:30 - 14:50	Wrap-up, NFDI4Chem services, and Q&A session

Notes:

- [Go through the time schedule of the workshop]

Further information:

- You don't necessarily need to mention every point on the agenda. Instead, give participants a general overview so they know what to expect from the workshop.

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Introduction

NFDI and NFDI4Chem

6

Notes:

- *Now, let's learn more about our organisation/project.*
- *Who has heard of the NFDI or the NFDI4Chem before today's workshop?*
- [for online workshops: let participants raise their virtual hands]

Further information:

- This part is used to give the participants some background information. They probably have never heard of the NFDI or NFDI4Chem. Keep this part short but informative.
- More information about the NFDI (in German): Survival Kit: Die Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur Deutschland (NFDI), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14981549>

- Founded in 2018 – funded by federal government and states as part of federal government’s digitalisation strategy
- Main goal:
 - Improvement and creation of Research Data Infrastructure & Management
 - Provision of tools, trainings and initiation of cultural change
- 27 consortia (26 discipline-specific + Base4NFDI)
- 5 sections (metadata, infra, edutrain, ELSA, industry)

Figure: Adaptation of “NFDI Consortia” by [Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur \(NFDI\) e.V.](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#) via [Zenodo](#) (adaptation: translation)

Notes:

- *The NFDI is the National Research Data Infrastructure or Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur and has the goal to establish exactly this. A research data infrastructure in Germany for handling research data in all fields.*
- *The NFDI consists of different consortia, each consortium is associated with a scientific field or a specific kind of data. Ideally each researcher should find at least one consortium that is providing information and support for their research. As you can see, the consortia are spread over all disciplines.*
- *Besides the consortia there are sections. In the sections topics are discussed that are important in all (or many) consortia and therefore a cooperation between these consortia is useful.*
- *NFDI not only wants to provide infrastructure but also develops standards, offers tools and trainings and wants to be a driving force for the cultural change in science.*

Further information:

- More information about the NFDI (in German): Survival Kit: Die Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur Deutschland (NFDI), <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14981549>
- If you know that not only chemists will join the workshop, maybe point the other useful consortia: <https://www.nfdi.de/consortia/?lang=en>

NFDI4Chem – who are we?

8

Notes:

- Who is the NFDI4Chem now. It is the consortium for chemistry. Roughly speaking we are comprised of members from the Research Community (Active researchers, e.g. at universities), Research Data Infrastructure institutions (e.g. KIT) & Learned societies such as the GDCh, DPhG and DBG.
- Existing experts got together to form the consortium. Therefore, we are a by-the-community for-the-community project.
- We are very grateful for our advisory boards from industry, community, international and publishers.

Further information:

- More information about the advisory boards: <https://www.nfdi4chem.de/the-advisory-boards/>
- A good overview of all participants of NFDI4Chem can be found here: <https://www.nfdi.de/consortia-nfdi4chem/?lang=en>

NFDI4Chem: Focus on molecules

9

Notes:

- NFDI4Chem focuses on the molecules. How to describe them with useful and standardised metadata, document associate reactions as well as analytical data like spectra and other investigations like biological activity.
- NFDI4Chem is developing tools and workflows to make handling data associated to molecules as easy as possible always focussing on the core of chemistry data: the molecules

Further information:

- -

NFDI4Chem: Vision

10

Notes:

- We aim to support researchers during the whole research process by fully digitising the data workflow from the earliest point in the lab to the final data publication. All according to the FAIR principles.
- FAIR is the backbone of modern research data management and is an acronym for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.
- To reach the goal of NFDI4Chem digitisation, standardisation and the community are important, to optimise and fit tools for handling research data, like electronic lab notebooks and repositories, to the needs of the chemistry community.

Further information:

- -

NFDI4Chem: Data handling from creation to re-use

Create Data
Smart Lab

Publish & Access Data
Repositories

Find & Use Data
**Metadata, Semantics
& Standards**

Get Support
Cultural Change

Notes:

- *NFDI4Chem supports you as a researcher through all your steps of your research from creating data to publishing and accessing data as well as finding data for reuse.*
- *NFDI4Chem is a driving force in the cultural change of handling research data more openly and changing to a healthy error culture in science.*

Further information:

- On error culture: <https://www.nfdi4chem.de/error-cultures-in-science/>

Who are we?

NFDI4Chem Task Area: Community and Training

Ann-Christin Andres
Johannes-Gutenberg-
University Mainz

Fabian Fink
RWTH Aachen
University

Dr. Annett Schröter
Friedrich Schiller
University Jena

Notes:

- [Introduce the workshop trainers]

Further information:

- Keep your introduction brief, but provide some information about yourself and your colleagues (e.g. your scientific background, workplace and recent projects).

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Introduction

Introduction of attendees

13

Notes:

- *Now I/we talked already a lot, but it is time to get to know you better. What is your scientific background and what are your expectations for the workshop.*

Further information:

- Time for the participants to get active. Emphasise that their participation and questions are important.
- Use this as a chance to establish the active involvement of the participants in this workshop. Get all participants talking, if possible/the group is not too large.

Introduction of attendees

- We would like to know more about you!
- Short poll:
 - Wait for the poll to start
 - Answer the questions

Notes:

- *Please take a few minutes to complete our short online poll so that we can learn more about you and why you have chosen to join our workshop today.*
- [Go through the results of the online poll]

Further information:

- Share the link to the online poll via the meeting chat (for online workshops) or place the (short) link as well as a QR code on the slide (for on-site workshops).
- The online poll of this workshop comprises the following six questions and corresponding answer options:
- *Which city do you work in?* [free text field]
- *What (specific) field of research do you work in?* [free text field]
- *Have you ever used a data management plan (DMP) in your research?* Yes, I use(d) a DMP in my research. / No, I never used a DMP.
- *Have you ever written a DMP yourself?* Yes, I wrote a DMP myself. / Yes, but I only started and never finished it. / No, I never wrote a DMP myself.
- *Have you ever used the software RDMO?* Yes, I use(d) RDMO in my work. / Yes, but only to try it out. / No, I never used RDMO./I don't know what RDMO is.
- *Why are you here today? And what would you like to learn about?* [free text field]

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Introduction

Data life cycle

15

Notes:

- *Now that you have a better understanding of who we are, and vice versa, let us dive in the basic concepts of research data management.*

Further information:

- -

Data life cycle

- Describes the lifespan of the data
- Based on various phases
- Different approaches to the same model depending on the institution, the funder, ...

Source: https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/knowledge_base/docs/data_life_cycle/ (accessed 2025-11-03)

16

Notes:

- As mentioned before, NFDI4Chem supports you during the whole research data life cycle (DLC).
- The DLC describes the lifespan of data and can be divided into different phases. The DLC can look different for different disciplines, but for chemistry the following six phases are useful: [go through the DLC phases]
- If you are searching for DLC you will find different approaches.

Further information:

- -

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Introduction

FAIR principles

17

Notes:

- *We have already heard that the FAIR principles form the backbone of modern research data management. Let us now take a closer look.*

Further information:

- -

FAIR principles

- Published in 2016 by FORCE11
- Guidelines to enhance reusability of data
- Increasingly important in science
- Part of DFG “Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice”

Source: <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Figure: “Publications and Data” by Auke Herrema licensed under [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) via [RDM Promotional Material](https://www.rdm-promotional-material.com/)

Notes:

- *The FAIR principles were first published in 2016. FAIR is an acronym for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. You will hear and see FAIR a lot during this workshop and by the end you will know the acronym by heart.*

Further information:

- You should at least once have read the article from 2016 ;)
- And be aware that „FAIR Principles put specific emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use the data, in addition to supporting its reuse by individuals.” -> taken from the abstract of the article

- Not all Open Data are FAIR, not all FAIR data are necessarily open

Figure: Adaptation of "FAIR and Open" by [Sarah Jones](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#) via [slideshare](#), accessed: 2025-12-05 (adaptation: colour and alignment)

Notes:

- *Open Science or Open Data and the FAIR principles are two concepts that are not identical but they complement each other. Not all Open Data is FAIR and not all FAIR data is necessarily open. If you have very FAIR data, then it will be open, and if you have really good documented Open Data it will be FAIR. So data that are FAIR and open have the greatest potential.*
- *Open Data -> make your data available for other to use*
- *FAIR data -> document your data in a way that reusing it is easy and ensured in the future*

Further information:

- -

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Data Management Plan

20

Notes:

- *Now that we have discussed briefly the basics of research data management, we would like to go over to the main topic of today's workshop: the Data Management Plan (DMP).*
- *A DMP is a useful tool that can help you organise your data handling within a project*

Further information:

- -

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Data Management Plan

Introduction

21

Notes:

- *So what is a Data Management Plan or DMP?*

Further information:

- -

What is a Data Management Plan (DMP)?

A DMP describes the handling of research data during and after a research project, it is a formal and at the same time a living document.

Figure: "Data Management Plan" by [The Turing Way](#) & [Scriberia](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#) via [Zenodo](#)

Source: <https://www.openaire.eu/community/blogs/why-is-this-a-good-data-management-plan> (accessed 2025-10-26)

22

Notes:

- *The Data Management Plan (DMP) helps to keep track of how data should be handled in a project.*
- *A DMP is both formal and living, meaning that it can and should be updated as soon as changes to the project require it.*

Further information:

- -

Elements of a DMP

Notes:

- A DMP answers all the W-questions: What was done/will be done with the data? How does the team take care of the data? Who is allowed to do what with the data when?
- [Go through some of the DMP elements]

Further information:

- You don't need to mention all the elements of a DMP that are listed on the slide. Instead, highlight some of the most important topics that will be covered in the workshop.

Benefits of a DMP

- Supports the research process
- Supports FAIR data
- Saves time in the long term
- Offers continuity
- Helps to consider issues related to confidentiality, ethics, security and copyright

24

Notes:

- *When used correctly, a DMP can offer a variety of benefits.*
- [Go through the information on the slide]
- *A DMP is a great tool for reflecting on your project and anticipating potential future problems (e.g. you may produce large amounts of data that need to be stored and archived at the end of the project). The DMP is also a fantastic tool for onboarding new people to a project, since it provides all the necessary information about responsibilities, the handling of research data, and the tools used in a central document.*
- *Yes, it takes some time at the beginning, but you will save time in the long run.*

Further information:

- It is important to discuss the benefits, since a DMP is often just seen as more paperwork without any benefits.
- You can find more information about DMPs in “The Turing Way”: <https://book.the-turing-way.org/reproducible-research/rdm/rdm-dmp/>

Requirements of funders - DFG

Checklist

Checklist must be submitted as part of proposal

1. Data description
2. Documentation and data quality
3. Storage and technical archiving the project
4. Legal obligations and conditions
5. Data exchange and long-term accessibility
6. Responsibility and resources

Released December 2021

Link to DFG checklist: [de/en](#) (accessed 2015-12-09)

Notes:

- *Let's have a look at the requirements of the German Research Foundation (DFG) concerning DMPs.*
- *There is no DMP, just a checklist. It is very important to them that it is not called a DMP.*
- *In a proposal, you must provide information about how you will handle data during and after the project.*
- *The checklist can be used as a set of guiding questions. You don't need to answer all of them, but doing so will help ensure that you have not overlooked any important aspects of research data management.*
- *The checklist consists of six topics.*

Further information:

- -

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Data Management Plan

Tools

26

Notes:

- *If we want to create a DMP now, there are various tools that can help us, ranging from checklists to software.*

Further information:

- -

Chemistry-specific DMP template

- NFDI4Chem developed a chemistry-specific DFG checklist
 - Enriched with information
 - Possible answer options
 - One or more free text fields per question
- Approach:
 - Survey on chemistry-specific aspects
 - Interviews on chemistry-specific DMP in 2022 + 2023
- Template on Zenodo:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948510>
- Template is also available at [NFDI4Chem RDMO instance](#) (accessed 2025-12-09)

Chemistry-Specific Catalog: DFG Checklist

The present questionnaire is a checklist issued by the German Research Foundation (DFG), enriched with chemistry-specific content and supplemented with necessary questions for better understanding and completeness. The DFG checklist must be submitted with your application and at the project's completion and is intended to assist you in structuring your data management. If you have any questions, please contact the central Research Data Management (RDM) team at your university or research institution, or reach out to NFDI4Chem at helpdesk@nfdi4chem.de.

The following questions are for describing chemical datasets generated and/or used in the project. The definition of what constitutes a dataset is an important conceptual decision that must be made individually for each institute or project. Choose a logical unit of your research data as a dataset, to which the same information regarding methodology, technology, accessibility, etc., applies. This can be, for example, a molecule, synthesis steps, the employed analysis method, similar simulation calculations, etc.

Categorising data into datasets helps assess the value of the data in terms of potential reuse and subsequent archiving. Since all questions must be answered for each individual dataset, an overly granular structure is not practical. Some aspects of data handling can be generalised and documented through accompanying policies. The preferred approach to managing data is typically communicated at the beginning of a project, either verbally or in writing, and is conveyed to subsequent doctoral candidates during their onboarding. An example of such a policy can be found from the Daumann Group at <https://www.cup.lmu.de/ac/daumann/erc-starting-grant-lanthanophor/research-data-management-plan/>

Section: Data Description

Question Set: Content Data Description

Question: How does your project generate new data?

Help: Research data is typically generated in every research project. Here, you should reflect upon and describe the ways in which you generate research data. The methods of data generation may vary depending on your specific chemical subdiscipline. Consider the methods and tools you use.

27

Notes:

- We already mentioned the DFG checklist, which contains general question about data handling. In NFDI4Chem we have developed a chemistry-specific version of the checklist, that supports you with finding the right answer, for example by providing answer options.
- [Go through the information on the slide]
- The checklist is also available for the popular DMP software RDMO.

Further information:

- Article about the DMP by NFDI4Chem: „Road to a Chemistry-Specific Data Management Plan“ <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2024-021>

Research Data Management Organiser

NFDI4Chem

Feedback Language

<https://rdmo.nfdi4chem.de/>
(accessed 2025-12-09)

Templates:

- Chemistry-specific DFG checklist
- Horizon Europe DMP
- Software Management Plan
- RDM policy generator

Figure: Screenshot of the [RDMO instance of NFDI4Chem](https://rdmo.nfdi4chem.de/) from 2025-12-09

28

Notes:

- *NFDI4Chem is hosting an Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) instance that is free of charge and that we will use in today's workshop. There you will find various templates.*
- [Go through the templates on the slide]

Further information:

- -

Sections of our DMP template

Section 1:
Data description

Section 2:
Documentation and data
quality

Section 3:
Storage and technical
security during the project

Section 4:
Data exchange and long-
term data accessibility

Section 5:
Legal obligations and
conditions

Section 6:
Responsibilities and
resources

29

Notes:

- *Our DMP template, the chemistry-specific DFG checklist, contains the following six sections:*
- *[Go through the sections on the slide]*
- *During the following hands-on part of our workshop, you will be guided through all six sections to create your own DMP.*

Further information:

- -

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Hands-on: Create your own DMP

30

Notes:

- *So, let's move on to the main part of today's workshop: creating your own DMP.*

Further information:

- Please allow time for any questions participants may have about the general introduction before moving on.

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Section 1

Data description

31

Notes:

- *The first section of our chemistry-specific Data Management Plan (DMP) template focuses on data description. Let's dive right in!*

Further information:

- -

Administrative data

- DMP version:
 - Date of first version
 - Date of last update

- Project information:
 - ID
 - Project name
 - Funder
 - Grant reference number
 - Project description
 - Name and ID (e.g., ORCID) of principal investigators and main researchers
 - Project data contact
 - Related policies

Source: https://www.dcc.ac.uk/sites/default/files/documents/resource/DMP_Checklist_2013.pdf (accessed 2025-12-16)

32

Notes:

- *As previously mentioned, our chemistry-specific DMP template is based on the DFG checklist, which serves a similar purpose.*
- *The checklist contains questions on how research data will be managed during the project. It serves as a guide to write the section “Handling of research data” as part of a DFG proposal.*
- *Unlike standard DMPs, it does not include administrative information, as these details are already covered elsewhere in the submitted project proposal.*
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- ORCID - Open Researcher and Contributor ID: ORCID is a free, unique, persistent identifier (PID) for individuals

Section 1: Questions

Content data description

- What kind of dataset is it?
- How does your project generate new data?
- Is existing data reused?

Technical data description

- Which data types (in terms of data formats) arise in your project?
- And in what way is the data further processed in your project?
- To what extent do these arise or what is the anticipated data volume?

Notes:

- *At the start of each section, we will show you the questions that you will be answering in your DMP during the self-working phase. Then, we will give you some background information on the topics involved.*
- [Go through the questions on the slide]

Further information:

- -

Research data

A legal definition (Directive (EU) 2019/1024):

"[...] documents in a digital form, other than scientific publications, which are collected or produced in the course of scientific research activities."

BUT: not always digital (e.g. documents, objects, samples)

DFG (2015):

"Research data include measurement data, laboratory values, audiovisual information, texts, survey data, objects from collections or samples that are created, developed or evaluated in scientific work. Methodological test procedures such as questionnaires, software and simulations can also represent central results of scientific research and should therefore also be included under the term research data. "

Source: „DFG Guidelines on the Handling of Research Data“, DFG 2015 (accessed 2025-12-05)

34

Notes:

- *Let's start with the definition of research data [read definitions] ...*
- *... so you see, data is not only digital and data is more than just results from a measurement, e.g., software.*

Further information:

- EU definition: Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (recast), Chapter 1, Article 2 "Definitions" (9) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1024/oj/eng>

Research data in chemistry

35

Notes:

- *Let us now take a look on the different kinds of data we have in chemistry.*
- [Go through the examples on the slide]

Further information:

- Think back to the introduction of the participants and the research fields they are working in, highlight the corresponding data here.

Introduction to file formats: Video

Figures: Video snapshots taken from "Knowledge clip: file formats" by [UGent Open Science](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#) via [YouTube](#), accessed: 2026-01-20

Notes:

- *To properly introduce the topic of file formats, we would like to show a video provided by the Open Science Team at Ghent University.*

Further information:

- Before the workshop, please ensure that the video and sound are working.
- Link to the video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kxxlQnc8u1I>

Data format standards

- Unencrypted, uncompressed, unpatented/non-proprietary, standardised, ideally open

Caution: open \neq non-proprietary

- If data is stored in a proprietary format (format of original software), it should always be stored in an open/archivable format as well, if possible.

Data type	Recommended	Not recommended
Table	CSV, TSV	XLS
Text	TXT, TEX, ODT, HTML, RTF	DOC
Video	FFmpeg, OpenH264, Xvid	MPEG-2, MPEG-4, MVC
Image	PNG, SVG	GIF, JPG, PSD, AI, PUB
Audio	WAV, FLAC, OPUS	WMA, MP3

Table: Adaption of table "Open Formats of Open Source Software" by [Roman Gerlach](#) et al. licensed under [CC0](#) via [Zenodo](#) (adapation: NFDI4Chem style, re-ordering)

37

Notes:

- To ensure interoperability and accessibility open and standardised data formats are important. This ensure that data can be handled independ from the software you are working with.*
- Proprietary file formats are owned/controlled by a company or organisation and usually require specific software or licences to read or edit the data.*
- [Go through information on the slide]

Further information:

-

Data format standards in chemistry

- Recommendations for data format standards and converters can be found in the [NFDI4Chem knowledge base](#).

Analytical method	Proprietary file extensions	Converter to open file format	File format
NMR spectroscopy	.fid, .mnova	MNova Topspin	JCAMP-DX, nmrML, NMReDATA
Mass spectrometry	.raw, .d, .baf,	Proteowizard	mzML
IR spectroscopy	.ispd, .icIR		JCAMP-DX
UV/vis spectroscopy	.dsw, .str, .bsk, .bkn, .ksd	proprietary software	comma-separated values (.csv)
HPLC	.xls	proprietary software	comma-separated values (.csv)

38

Notes:

- The slide summarises the recommendations for data format standards and converters for various analytical methods.
- [Go through information on the slide]
- Data standardisation is an ongoing process in NFDI4Chem. It is beneficial to check the knowledge base regularly.*

Further information:

- The table itself is no longer available in the NFDI4Chem knowledge base, but the information it contains is still accessible.
- If possible, adapt this slide to the data formats with which the participants work.

Self-working phase

1. Go to RDMO to start writing your own DMP
2. Create a new project by using **+New project**
3. Add a title and a short description
4. Choose the **NDFI4Chem_Template** as catalog
➡ Create the project
5. Click on **Answer questions**
6. Define one dataset for your project
7. Answer the questions in the section **data description**

39

Notes:

- *Now it's time for our first self-working phase. We will therefore show you the steps on this slide in RDMO. You will then repeat these steps and fill in your answers for the section on data description.*
- [Head to the RDMO instance used for the workshop (e.g. <https://rdmo.nfdi4chem.de/>) and demonstrate how to log in and create a new project. Then, demonstrate some of the possibilities mentioned below when writing a DMP in RDMO.]
- *Before you start, consider your data structure and define a dataset.*
- [Name some good practice examples for defining datasets in an RDMO project.]
- [Leave room for solving technical problems and answering questions.]

Further information:

- In RDMO, square checkboxes allow multiple answers to be selected, while round radio buttons allow only one choice. This visual distinction helps users clearly identify whether a question expects a decision or multiple applicable options.
- “Reuse answers” copies existing answers from another dataset.
- “Apply this answer to all tabs where this question is empty” propagates the current answer to all other datasets without a value.
- The eraser icon deletes the current dataset definition.

Discussion

Which aspects of defining your dataset were most challenging for you?

Did you find it difficult to define the scope or boundaries of your dataset?

Does the template provide all the answers you need for your project?

40

Notes:

- *Now that you have completed the data description section of your DMP, we would like to discuss your experiences and difficulties.*
- [Go through the guiding questions on the slide]

Further information:

- Use the guiding questions on the slide to lead the discussion.
- Encourage participants to actively contribute to the discussion.
- If there is little or no feedback, ask one or two participants to present their completed DMP and discuss any problems they encountered.
- If there is too much feedback within the allotted time, ask participants to type their remaining questions in the chat (for online workshops) or save them for the next break (for onsite workshops).

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Section 2

Documentation and data quality

41

Notes:

- *The next section of our chemistry-specific DMP template is on documentation and data quality. Let's continue!*

Further information:

- -

Section 2: Questions

Documentation

- What approaches are being taken to describe the data in a comprehensible manner (such as the use of available metadata, documentation standards or ontologies)?
- What digital methods and tools (e.g. software) are required to use the data?

Data quality

- What measures are being adopted to ensure high data quality?
- Are quality controls in place and if so, how do they operate?

Notes:

- *As before, we will show you the questions that you will be answering in your DMP during the self-working phase. Then, we will give you some background information on the topics involved.*
- [Go through the questions on the slide]

Further information:

- -

Naming conventions

Figure: "Documents" by [xkcd](https://xkcd.com) licensed under [CC BY-NC 2.5](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/2.5/) via xkcd.com, accessed: 2025-12-09

PRO TIP: NEVER LOOK IN SOMEONE ELSE'S DOCUMENTS FOLDER.

Notes:

- First, let's take a short look at naming conventions. Have you ever looked through someone else's folder? Perhaps you felt the same way as the people in this comic.

Further information:

- -

README

- A README is a simple text (.txt) or markdown (.md) file
- Contains metadata about data and/or folder structure, e.g. naming conventions, data types
- Very flexible and easy to use and reuse
- Makes your data more understandable and easy to get into
- Content may vary depending on the purpose
 - Internal documentation
 - Accompanying document for data publication

Notes:

- *A simple way to document naming conventions, folder structures, or information about a dataset is to create a 'README' file. These files are flexible and can be used in any context. You can use them to document your own folder structures and file names, as well as to provide additional information about the data.*
- *README files are very common when publishing data.*

Further information:

- It could also be very interesting to take a look at the info file format:
<https://doi.org/10.1039/D2DD00131D>

Metadata

What is metadata and why is it important?

- Data that describes data
- Makes datasets searchable (and findable)
- Makes datasets understandable and FAIR
- Machine- and human-readable
- Standardisation is ongoing

Figure: "Data for future generations" by [Auke Herrema](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#) via [RDM Promotional Material](#)

Source: <https://www.openaire.eu/what-is-metadata?highlight=WyJtZXRhZGF0YSJd> (accessed 2025-11-03)

45

Notes:

- We already mentioned metadata on the last slide. So, what is this metadata? Well, metadata is data about data.
- It describes the data, making it searchable, findable, and ultimately FAIR. Metadata should be both machine- and human-readable, and the standardisation of metadata documentation is an ongoing process.
- The cartoon on the right illustrates this well. When other people find your data in five years' time, will they actually know what was done? By whom? Under which experimental conditions? It's not just other people who need to know this information, but you yourself too. Do you remember everything about the data you collected 10 years ago?

Further information:

- -

Metadata schema and standards

Metadata Schema

- Determines and structures the metadata elements
- Pairs of **metadata element - value**
- Defines input type
- Sets restrictions, such as the use of (controlled) vocabulary or required fields

Metadata Standard

- Schema that have undergone a review process
- Usually in their respective community
- Common examples: ISO, DIN, and EN standard

Notes:

- *Metadata schemas define the overall structure of metadata. In a metadata schema, information always consists of two parts: the metadata element and the value of that element.*
- *For example, if you want to document a temperature, the metadata element would be 'temperature' and the value would be the actual temperature, such as 25 °C.*
- *A schema provides a clear structure in which you can set restrictions, use controlled vocabularies, and mark some information as required. In general, anyone can define their own metadata schema.*
- *A metadata standard is a schema that a community has agreed upon. This includes agreeing upon language, spelling, date formats, input types and so on. The advantage of using a metadata schema is that data can be easily compared.*

Further information:

- -

Dublin Core

International Data Exchange format

- Describes digital or physical web resources
- 22 elements – 15 with an ISO certificate
- Refinements and encoding schemes for subject specific applications
- For more information:
 - <http://www.dublincore.org/>
 - <https://www.dublincore.org/resources/userguide/>

Notes:

- One metadata standard is the Dublin Core Metadata Schema. Consisting of 15 main metadata items, it is used to describe digital or physical resources (i.e. documents and objects on the web).
- It was the first metadata standard for describing web content. It enables the description of digital resources, including their origin, licence and technical details.
- There are also refinements and encoding schemas for subject-specific applications.

Further information:

- The Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) is responsible for formulating the Dublin Core.
- Instantiation (German: Instanziierung) is the process of creating a new object and allocating it a location.

Controlled vocabulary

- An organised arrangement of words with a defined scope
- Promotes consistency and allows the variability of used terms as well as context and relationships

48

Notes:

- *Let's head over to controlled vocabulary. A controlled vocabulary is an organised arrangement of words with a defined scope. It promotes consistency and allows variability in the terms used, as well as including context and relationships.*
- *For example, it could be a simple word list used to fill a metadata field. This leads to more uniform and comparable entries and avoids typos.*
- *In addition, a taxonomy provides information about hierarchical relationships (or classification). This is known from the animal and plant kingdoms, which are organised hierarchically into classes with certain characteristics.*
- *A thesaurus is an organised collection of related terms. One example is the Getty Thesaurus of Geographic Names. This uses equivalent terms for place names (e.g. Aachen, Bad Aachen or Aquisgrana) and you can also identify hierarchical relationships by knowing that Aachen is in North Rhine-Westphalia (NRW) and that North Rhine-Westphalia is in Germany.*
- *Ontologies are formal, machine-readable specifications of a conceptual model. We won't discuss ontologies in too much detail, but we will see an example of their usage on the next slide.*

Further reading:

- -

Example: Use of CHMO ontology in Chemotion

The screenshot shows the Chemotion interface for an analysis. At the top, the chemical structure of ethyl 5-phenylthiophene-2-sulfonate is displayed with its molecular formula $C_{12}H_{12}O_3S_2$ and exact mass 268.022786 g/mol. Below this, the analysis is identified as "1H NMR" with a status of "Confirmed". The interface includes tabs for Properties, Analyses, QC & curation, References, and Results. A table below the analysis details shows the name "1H NMR" and its status "Confirmed". An orange arrow points to the "Type (Chemical Methods Ontology)" field, which is set to "1H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (1H NMR)".

Figure: "Class tree of CHMO showing 1H NMR" as depicted by [NFDI4Chem Terminology Service](#) (id:CHMO:0000593), accessed: 2026-01-04

The screenshot shows the Chemotion search interface. The search bar contains the text "1h n". A dropdown menu is open, showing the search results "1H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (1H NMR)". The Chemotion ELN logo is visible in the top right corner.

49

Notes:

- Using an ontology can improve the findability of data, especially if you use it during the data documentation step.
- In the top right corner, you can see part of the class tree of the Chemical Methods Ontology (CHMO) with an example of 1H-NMR.
- On the left, you can see how it is used in the Chemotion electronic lab notebook (ELN) during the documentation of your analysis. Selecting the correct method from the ontology ensures that the data can be easily found later. Using the ontology avoids confusion caused by synonyms, different spellings or language.
- On the bottom right, you can see a search for data in the Chemotion Repository. We can now search for all 1H-NMR data using the corresponding CHMO term.
- Using ontologies from the outset ensures data findability in the long term.

Further information:

- -

What is an ELN?

Basic System (not an ELN)

- Text entries
- Attachments
- Annotation
- Search function
- Sharing via the cloud

e.g. Evernote, GoogleDrive, Dropbox, MS Sharepoint

Electronic Lab Notebooks

- + Structured metadata in human- and machine-readable formats
- + Templates
- + Discipline-specific functions/ editors
- + Basic inventory management
- + Rights management
- + Audit trail
- + API (Application Programming Interface)

e.g. Labfolder, eLabFTW

High end systems

- + Customer relationship management (CRM)
- + Inventory management
- + Workflows
- + Link to lab equipment
- + Analysis and data mining
- + Electronic signatures
- + Reporting or statistics modules

e.g. Limesophy LIMS

Source: <https://doi.org/10.4126/FRL01-006425772>

50

Notes:

- *Let's take a look at what an electronic lab notebook actually is.*
- *A very simple solution is the so-called 'blank sheet' system. These solutions allow you to enter text, add attachments and annotations, and sometimes include search functions and the ability to share content via the cloud. Examples include Google Drive, Dropbox and MS SharePoint, among others. However, these are not what we would call electronic lab notebooks.*
- *An ELN has additional functionalities; the most important of these is the ability to document structured metadata in human- and machine-readable formats. It has options to create templates and/or discipline-specific functions. It also has rights management to control who has access to which data. Examples here are LabFolder and eLabFTW.*
- *Then there are the 'high-end systems', also known as LIMS (laboratory information management systems). These have even more functionality*
- [Go through information on the slide]

Further information:

- When discussing electronic lab notebooks, it is important to manage expectations. An ELN is a place to document your research, not to carry out all the analysis and calculations.

Advantages of an ELN

Avoid Data Loss

- Linking experimental descriptions to collected data (analog and digital)
- Secure data storage, backups

Standardised Documentation

- Structured and standardised collection of metadata
- Generation of interoperable (meta)data

Knowledge Management

- Data are findable
- Data are accessible
- Data are available, even after change of personnel!

Publication

- Data provision for publication of research results
- Simple transfer of data to repositories

Notes:

- *So why should you consider to use an ELN?*
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information

- -

How to choose an ELN?

- There is no one „ELN to rule them all“
- How can one ELN cater to the needs of a whole university?
- Need to select the right ELN for the job

Figure: "Website ELN Finder"
accessed: 2026-01-04

<https://eln-finder.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/home>

52

Notes:

- *To select an ELN, you need to define your requirements and those of the potential ELN. The problem is that there is no single ELN that works for all research fields. This makes it difficult for infrastructure providers, such as IT centres and university libraries, to offer a centralised tool that meets the needs of all users. Therefore, you need to select the right tool for you. If you know your requirements, tools like the ELN Finder can help.*
- *The ELN Finder, a database of electronic lab notebooks created by the university library at TU Darmstadt, allows you to search for a suitable ELN using filters.*

Further information:

- Many universities are starting to offer general electronic laboratory notebooks (ELNs) as a centralised solution (e.g. eLabFTW). However, as it is a generic solution, it may not be the right tool for everyone.

Self-working phase

1. Go back to your RDMO project
2. Answer the questions in the [documentation and data quality](#) section for the one dataset you created earlier on

Notes:

- *Now it's time for our next self-working phase. Therefore, go back to your RDMO project and answer the questions in the section on documentation and data quality for the dataset you created earlier.*
- [Leave room for solving technical problems and questions]

Further information:

- In RDMO, square checkboxes allow multiple answers to be selected, while round radio buttons allow only one choice. This visual distinction helps users clearly identify whether a question expects a decision or multiple applicable options.
- “Reuse answers” copies existing answers from another dataset.
- “Apply this answer to all tabs where this question is empty” propagates the current answer to all other datasets without a value.
- The eraser icon deletes the current dataset definition.

Discussion

What difficulties did you encounter in the self-working phase?

Did you find the answer options sufficient to complete the template?

Are data quality and control measures already established at your site?

Notes:

- *Now that you have filled in the documentation and data quality section of your DMP, we would like to discuss your experiences and difficulties.*
- [Go through the guiding questions on the slide]

Further information:

- Lead the discussion by using the guiding questions on the slide.
- Motivate participants to actively take part in the discussion.
- If there is little or no feedback, ask one or two participants to present what they filled out in their DMP and whether they encountered any problems.
- If there is too much feedback within the allotted time, ask the participants to type their remaining questions in the chat (online workshop) or to save their questions for the next break (onsite workshop).

Break

Notes:

- *Now it's time for a 10 minutes break. See you again at ...*

Further information:

- Note when the workshop will continue (online workshop: in the chat; on-site workshop: on a whiteboard or flipchart).

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Section 3

Storage and technical security during the project

56

Notes:

- *Welcome back! We hope you enjoyed your short break. Now, let's move on to the next section of our chemistry-specific DMP template, which covers storage and technical security during the project.*

Further information:

- -

Section 3: Questions

Data storage during the project

- How is the data to be stored and archived throughout the project duration?
- How are the generated or existing physical samples linked to the data during the project's duration?

Technical data security during the project

- What is in place to secure sensitive data in this dataset throughout the project duration (access and usage rights)?

Notes:

- *As before, we will show you the questions you will answer in your DMP during the self-working phase. Then, we will give you some background information on the topics involved.*
- [Go through the questions on the slide]

Further information:

- -

Different types of data preservation

- Active data
- Access for the data producer
- Data kept short-term
- Purpose: Protection and discovery

Backup

- Final Data
- Access for the data producer
- Data kept long-term
- Purpose: Preservation of information

Archiving

- Final Data
- Open access
- Data persistence depends on the publishing institution
- Purpose: Provision of data for reuse

Publication

Notes:

- *There are three types of data preservation.*
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- -

Common causes of data loss

Hardware error

Accidents & disasters

Malware & hacking

Software error

User error

Loss & theft

Figure: Adaptation of "CompFrontSmall" by [pyroclastichawk](#) licensed under [CC BY 2.0](#) via [flickr](#) (adaptation: picture is cropped)

Interested in more?

[Research Data ScaryTales of TKFDM](#)

Notes:

- *The slide summarises some common causes of data loss.*
- [Go through information on the slide]

Further information:

- TKFDM: Thuringian Network for Research Data Management
- The Research Data ScaryTales are a card game that is similar to black stories. The short stories show what scary consequences mistakes in data management can have.
- For more information visit their website: <https://forschungsdaten-thueringen.de/rdm-scarytales/articles/overview.html>

Criteria for selecting data storage (1/2)

1. Storage space & place (physical & virtual)

- Availability of required data volume
- How many storage locations and devices am I using?
Keep this number low!

2. Backup plan

- Backup frequency (daily, weekly)
- Number of copies needed
- Automation
- Storage duration
- Full vs. incremental vs. differential

Notes:

- *So, how to avoid data loss?*
- [Go through information on the slide]

Further information:

- Differences between full, incremental and differential backups
 - Full backup: comprise entire data backup sets, regardless of already existing backups or data change circumstances.
 - Incremental backup: comprise data files that have changed since the most recently completed full backup.
 - Differential backup: comprise data files that have changed since the most recently completed full or incremental backup.
 - Check here for more information or examples:
<https://www.acronis.com/en/blog/posts/incremental-differential-backups/>

Criteria for selecting data storage (2/2)

3. Versioning

- Need to keep track of different versions?
- Manually vs automatically (e.g. git)

4. Access & Security

- Shared access (e.g. collaborators, remote working?)
- Protection against manipulation and loss (password needed?, encryption?)
- Legal constraints (e.g. data privacy)

5. Responsibility

- Am I in charge? Or my IT support?

Notes:

- [Go through information on the slide]

Further information:

- -

Lifespan of storage media

- Lifespan of storage media is restricted
- New hard drive storage every 2-5 years

Graphic is based on: <https://www.computerwoche.de/article/2867723/ratgeber-langzeitarchivierung-dateiformate-und-speichemedien.html>
(accessed 2025-11-04)

62

Notes:

- *Did you know that you should periodically check your stored data and transfer it to new storage media or devices? This is because storage media has a limited lifespan. The lifespan of a regularly used hard drive is quite short.*
- [Go through information on the slide]

Further information:

- If you need more information on the lifetime of storage media, check the source provided for the graphic.

The 3-2-1 rule for backups

Use the possibility of an automatic backup!
Regularly check the backup for recoverability and readability!

63

Notes:

- How many of you have heard of the 3-2-1 rule for backups?
- [Go through information on the slide]
- Remember what we discussed at the beginning: backups are for active data. If you don't have backups of the data you've been working with recently (e.g. during the past week), that would be a good place to start.

Further information:

- More information about the 3-2-1 backup rule: <https://nfdi4chem.de/3-2-1-rule/>
- Be aware that there are also other backup strategies like 3-1-2, 3-2-1-1 or 3-2-1-1-0, not too important for the participants but good-to-know: <https://www.baculasystems.com/blog/321-vs-3211-vs-32110-backup-rules/>

Data versioning

Why is it important?

- Traceability (tracking of changes with timestamp and user ID)
- Reproducibility of workflows
- Facilitates collaboration
- Possibility to reset to previous version if necessary

Figure: <https://github.com/CSSEGSandData/COVID-19> (accessed 2025-11-04)

Notes:

- One important aspect of data backup is to make sure to keep track of different versions. This is called version control.
- Here is an example for COVID-19 data on GitHub. You can find the daily reported COVID-19 number of cases here. With GitHub's version control, you can see exactly what data was added or changed and when.
- [Go through information on the slide]

Further information:

- -

Data versioning: manual vs automatic

Manual versioning

- Use file naming convention to document file version (v01, v02,...)
- Use archive subfolder for older versions
- Create and maintain versioning table to document all changes to data (and documents)
 - File name, date of change, author, comment on what was changed

Automatic versioning

- Changes are automatically tracked
- Facilitates collaborative work on data and documents
- Built-in functions (e.g. cloud services)
- Use specific version control software

Notes:

- *In general, one can differentiate between manual and automatic versioning.*
- [Go through information on the slide]

Further information:

- -

Technical data security

Certain types of research data require special protection due to legal, commercial, or contractual reasons.

- Personal data
- Patents
- Industry collaborations
- Confidential and sensitive data

- Access and usage rights
- Confidentiality agreements/ Non-Disclosure Agreements (NDAs)

Notes:

- *Certain types of research data require special protection due to legal, commercial or contractual reasons.*
- *It is therefore important to consider the appropriate security measures for sensitive data throughout the project (e.g. access rights).*
- *In chemistry, when sensitive data is mentioned, it does not usually refer to personal data. Sensitive data often arises in projects involving industrial collaborations.*
- *Data can become sensitive during a project when considerations relating to patents arise. Access and usage rights are then documented in confidentiality agreements, also known as non-disclosure agreements (NDAs).*

Further information:

- Describe how access could be regulated, particularly in the event of any restrictions, and mention the tools that could be used for this purpose.

Rights and role management (1/2)

- Ensure that **access rights** are clearly defined and documented:
 - Who has access to what, and who determines this?
 - Who determines which access rights users have?
 - Who is responsible for maintaining access rights (i.e. granting and revoking them)?
 - How often are access rights reviewed?
 - Which data require access rights?
 - How and where should the above be documented?

67

Notes:

- *Thinking about rights and roles in your project is essential and important throughout the entire data life cycle.*
- *The answers to all the questions on this slide should be included in the data management plan.*
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- -

Rights and role management (2/2)

- Use strong passwords!
 - <https://help.lafayette.edu/guidelines-for-strong-passwords/>
- Use password managers
 - e.g., [KeePass](#)

Notes:

- *Remember to use strong passwords – a password manager can make this much easier.*

Further information:

- -

Group work

Breakout session

Discuss the following aspects in your group and make notes on the provided whiteboard:

- Suitable storage solutions
- Linking options for data and physical samples

Notes:

- *Now, let's discuss data storage in more detail.*
- *Please consider suitable storage solutions and linking options for data and physical samples, and discuss these in groups.*
- *You will therefore be assigned to breakout rooms.*
- *Take some notes during your group work. The results will be presented later in the discussion.*

Further information:

- Group the participants into groups of 4–6 people.
- For online workshops, create breakout rooms in advance and provide participants with an online whiteboard using your preferred tool. The whiteboard should contain the exercise description and enough space for notes.
- For on-site workshops, distribute the groups around the room and provide note-taking materials if necessary.

Self-working phase

Answer the questions in the [storage and technical security during the project](#) section.

Consideration: Do the answers provided in the template match the solutions you discussed earlier in the group work?

70

Notes:

- *Now, let's move on to the next self-working phase. Go back to your RDMO project and answer the questions in the storage and technical security section for the dataset you created earlier.*
- *Consider the group discussion while filling in your DMP.*
- [Leave room for solving technical problems and answering questions.]

Further information:

- In RDMO, square checkboxes allow multiple answers to be selected, while round radio buttons allow only one choice. This visual distinction helps users clearly identify whether a question expects a decision or multiple applicable options.
- “Reuse answers” copies existing answers from another dataset.
- “Apply this answer to all tabs where this question is empty” propagates the current answer to all other datasets without a value.
- The eraser icon deletes the current dataset definition.

Discussion

What difficulties did you encounter in the group work / self-working phase?

Are the results of your group work similar to the answers in the template?

What additional options have you identified?

Notes:

- *Now that you have filled in the storage and technical security during the project section of your DMP, we would like to discuss your experiences and difficulties.*
- [Go through the guiding questions on the slide]

Further information:

- Lead the discussion by using the guiding questions on the slide.
- Motivate participants to actively take part in the discussion.
- If there is little or no feedback, ask one or two participants to present what they filled out in their DMP and whether they encountered any problems.
- If there is too much feedback within the allotted time, ask the participants to type their remaining questions in the chat (online workshop) or to save their questions for the next break (onsite workshop).

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Section 4

Data exchange and long-term data accessibility

72

Notes:

- *The next section of our chemistry-specific DMP template covers data exchange and long-term accessibility of data. Let's move on!*

Further information:

- -

Section 4: Questions

Reuse

- Is this data set especially suitable for use in other contexts?
- Which criteria are used to select research data to make it available for subsequent use by others?
- When is the research data available for use by third parties?

Archiving

- How do you archive your data and in which suitable infrastructure?
- Are embargo periods to be observed? If so, how long are they?
- How are the physical samples archived, and how are data linked to the physical samples?

Restrictions on publication

- Do you anticipate any implications or restrictions regarding subsequent publication or accessibility?

73

Notes:

- *The slide summarises the questions that should be addressed in Section 4 of the self-working phase.*
- [Go through the questions on the slide]

Further information:

- -

What is a licence?

- A licence is a contractually agreed right of use.
- It is granted by the copyright holder to another party to use the copyrighted work in specific ways,
 - to copy it,
 - to modify it,
 - to make it digitally accessible
 - or to use it commercially.

Notes:

- *An important topic when it comes to data exchange and publication is licensing.*
- *Without a clear licence, proper reuse of data is not possible.*
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- -

Licences and their openness

Licence model	Processing prohibited	Commercial use prohibited	Copyleft	Attribution	Copyright waiver / waiver of rights to enforcement
Creative Commons	CC-BY-NC-ND, CC-BY-ND	CC-BY-NC-SA, CC-BY-NC	CC-BY-SA	CC-BY	CC0
Open Data Commons			Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL)	Open Data Commons Attribution License	Open Data Commons Public Domain Dedication and License (PDDL)
Community Data License Agreement			CDLA-Sharing-1.0	CDLA-Permissive-2.0.	

Source: Adaptation of "Lizenzen und Ihre Offenheit" by [Cora Assmann](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#) via [Zenodo](#) (adaptation: translation and colour)

Notes:

- *Let's take a look at some licences for data and how open they are.*
- *Creative Commons licences are widely used, but there are also other licences for publishing data. Here, you will find a comparison of the Creative Commons licences, the Open Data Commons and the Community Data Licence Agreement.*
- *Please note that Creative Commons licences were originally designed for legally secure licencing of creative content rather than data, whereas Open Data Commons has developed standard licences specifically for data. However, this is not yet common practice.*
- *As you can see, only the CC licences offer very strict options.*

Further information:

- Open Data Commons Licences: <https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/>
- Community Data License Agreement: <https://cdla.dev/> (Version 1.0 was "was designed to embody the principles of copyleft in a data license")

Different types of data preservation

- Active data
- Access for the data producer
- Data kept short-term
- Purpose: Protection and discovery

Backup

- Final Data
- Access for the data producer
- Data kept long-term
- Purpose: Preservation of information

Archiving

- Final Data
- Open access
- Data persistence depends on the publishing institution
- Purpose: Provision of data for reuse

Publication

Notes:

- *Let's go back to the overview slide. We already discussed backups in the previous section. Now, we will focus on the archiving and publication of data.*

Further information:

- -

The 4 steps of data preservation

1. What to keep? Data selection
2. How to keep? Prepare data and files for the preservation
3. Where to keep? Suitable location or medium
4. Perform periodic checks of the preserved data

77

Notes:

- *First, let us take a closer look at the four steps of data preservation.*
- *You should identify which data to keep, for example data that form the basis of a published research paper, irretrievable measurements and observations, or data that is expensive to sample or collect.*
- *In order to prepare the data for preservation, you should include documentation (e.g. a readme file), organise the files, use suitable file formats, and use archive folders that are separate from the files that are actively in use.*
- *Store your archived data in a suitable location (an archive or a repository with an archive function) and periodically check the readability and integrity of the files.*

Further information:

- -

Reasons for data publication

Figure: By [Brian Hole](#) licensed under [CC BY 4.0](#) via [figshare](#)

Notes:

- *In addition to archiving, publishing data can ensure its preservation. There are many good reasons to publish data.*
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- -

FAIR principles

According to the DFG's guidelines on good research practice, research data must be FAIR!

DFG GRP Code of Conduct Guideline 13

Providing public access to research results:

"[...] whenever possible researchers make the research data and principal materials on which a publication is based available in recognised archives and repositories in accordance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable)."

Source: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281892>

79

Notes:

- As you may recall, FAIR stands for findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable.
- Guideline 13 of the GRP, 'Providing public access to research results', requires: [Read the guideline].
- The FAIR principles' requirements for machine readability are quite technical, and it is often the infrastructure that is responsible for meeting these requirements (e.g. the repository where you publish your data) rather than you as a researcher.

Further information:

- -

How can I publish my data?

Supplement of an article in scientific journal

Data Journal

Data Repository

Notes:

- There are three main ways to publish data. These are: in the supporting information; in a data journal; and in a data repository.
- In the following, we will focus on data repositories.

Further information:

- -

Data repositories

81

Notes:

- There are three main types of repository: generic, domain-specific, and institutional.
- [Go through the information on the slide and explain some examples]

Further information:

- EDMOND: Max Planck Society
- DaRUS: Stuttgart
- REFODAT: Thüringen
- TU datalib: TU Darmstadt

Data repository selection criteria

- Long-term availability (Certification?)
- Provision of a PID (e.g. DOI, URN, ARK)
- Licence (e.g. Open Access, Restricted)
- Domain-specific or institutional
- Data curation options

[re3data.org](https://www.re3data.org) is a helpful tool for finding a suitable data repository.

Figure: Adaptation of "Figure 2. The re3data.org icon system" by Heinz Pampel et al. licensed under [CC BY 3.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/) via [PLOS ONE](https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0151111) (adaptation: figure is cropped)

Notes:

- [Go through information on the slide]
- *Re3data is a useful tool for finding the right repository for your data.*
- *It contains over 3,400 repository records covering all disciplines. It also provides an overview of the features offered by each one.*

Further information:

- Number of listed repositories in re3data (<https://www.re3data.org/>): 3454 (access 2025-12-18)

Group work

Breakout session

Discuss the following aspects in your group and make notes on the provided whiteboard:

- What strategies exist at your site for the backup, archiving, and publication of your research data?
- Have you ever published your data in a repository?
If so, did you choose a generic or domain-specific repository?

83

Notes:

- *Let's move on to the next group activity. Please go to your group and discuss the following aspects:*
- [Go through the aspects on the slide]
- *You will therefore be assigned to breakout rooms.*
- *Take some notes during your group work. The results will be presented later in the discussion.*

Further information:

- Group the participants into groups of 4–6 people.
- For online workshops, create breakout rooms in advance and provide participants with an online whiteboard using your preferred tool. The whiteboard should contain the exercise description and enough space for notes.
- For on-site workshops, distribute the groups around the room and provide note-taking materials if necessary.

Self-working phase

Answer the questions in the [data exchange and long-term data accessibility](#) section.

Consideration: Do the answers provided in the template match the strategies and ideas you discussed earlier in the group work?

Notes:

- *Let's continue with the next self-working phase.*
- *Go back to your RDMO project and answer the questions in the data exchange and long-term accessibility section for the dataset you created earlier.*
- *Bear in mind the group discussion while filling in your DMP.*
- [Leave room for solving technical problems and questions]

Further information:

- In RDMO, square checkboxes allow multiple answers to be selected, while round radio buttons allow only one choice. This visual distinction helps users clearly identify whether a question expects a decision or multiple applicable options.
- “Reuse answers” copies existing answers from another dataset.
- “Apply this answer to all tabs where this question is empty” propagates the current answer to all other datasets without a value.
- The eraser icon deletes the current dataset definition.

Discussion

What difficulties did you encounter in the group work / self-working phase?

Did you find the answer options sufficient to complete the template?

Have you identified additional answer options in your group / on your own?

Notes:

- *Now that you have completed the data exchange and long-term accessibility section of your DMP, we would like to discuss your experiences and any difficulties you have encountered.*
- [Go through the guiding questions on the slide]

Further information:

- Lead the discussion by using the guiding questions on the slide.
- Motivate participants to actively take part in the discussion.
- If there is little or no feedback, ask one or two participants to present what they filled out in their DMP and whether they encountered any problems.
- If there is too much feedback within the allotted time, ask the participants to type their remaining questions in the chat (online workshop) or to save their questions for the next break (onsite workshop).

Lunch

Notes:

- *Now it's time for an one hour lunch break. See you again at ...*

Further information:

- Note when the workshop will continue (online workshop: in the chat; on-site workshop: on a whiteboard or flipchart).

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Section 5

Legal obligations and conditions

87

Notes:

- *Welcome back! We hope you enjoyed your lunch. Now, let's move on to the next section of our chemistry-specific DMP template, which covers legal obligations and conditions.*

Further information:

- -

Section 5: Questions

Legal restrictions

- What is in place to consider aspects of use and copyright law as well as ownership issues?
- What are the legal specifics associated with the handling of research data in your project?

Scientific specifics

- Are there any significant research codes or professional standards to be taken into account?

Notes:

- *As usual, we will show you the questions that you will be answering in your DMP during the self-working phase. After that, we will give you some background information on the topics involved.*
- [Go through the questions on the slide]

Further information:

- -

Disclaimer

- This session is designed for informational purposes only and does not substitute legal consultation.
- We assume no liability for the accuracy of the information presented.
- The NFDI has established a section to work on legal aspects in research data management.
- For any concrete questions on legal aspects, contact the legal office of your university or research institution!

Notes:

- [Read the slide]
- *We are no lawyers and the German law is complicated.*
- *We are not allowed to give legal advice.*
- *We only provide information and point out some of the main aspects of the legal framework.*

Further information:

- -

Research data policies

- Guidance on how to handle research data
- Provide an overview of
 - Responsibilities for research data management
 - Available infrastructure and support services
- Different types of policies required by

Source: https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/ijkjlb2g/se_rdm_best_practices.pdf (accessed 2025-10-26)

International organisations

Publisher

Funder

Institution

e.g., university or research centers

Discipline-specific

e.g., GLP, DFG Review Board
[Chemistry](#),
[Physics](#), [Material science](#)

Source: <https://www.forschungsdaten.info/praxis-kompakt/english-pages/guidelines-and-policies/> (accessed 2025-10-26)

Source: <https://www.dfg.de/en/research-funding/funding-initiative/research-data/recommendations> (accessed 2025-10-26)

Notes:

- Policies can give us guidance on how to handle research data, and there are different type of these policies:
- [Go through the information on the slide]
- If you are not familiar with the research data policy of your institution, your funder and publisher, please familiarise yourself with these policies.

Further information:

- -

DFG “Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice” (2019)

- Fundamental revision of the recommendations from 1998
- Modifications:
 - Multidimensional approach
 - Codex with 19 guidelines
 - 11 guidelines on the research process
 - RDM is relevant in 8 of these 11 guidelines

Figure: “Structure of the DFG Code of Conduct Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice” *Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft* licensed under CC BY-SA 4.0 via [Zenodo](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281892)

Source: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281892>

Notes:

- [Go through the information on the slides]
- *A multidimensional approach:*
- *The definition of the guideline is very abstract and not very detailed.*
- *Explanation of the guideline: provides more detailed information about the guideline.*
- *Detailed, subject-specific information: Provides specific information relating to specific scientific fields, making the guideline more understandable.*

Further information:

- The graphic on the slide is taken from the “Guideline for Safeguarding Good Research Practice” version 2 from 2022 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6472827>). In version 3 from 2025 (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14281892>) the graphic is no longer included

Who “owns“ research data?

You can own only physical objects!

No ownership of data!

You can own the rights on the data, in case they are part of another protected right (e.g. copyright, patent law, business secret).

Notes:

- *First of all, you only can own physical objects. You can have ownership of a laptop, car or real estate, but there is no ownership of data. What you can own is the right on data in case they are part of another protected right, e.g., copyright, patent law or a business secret.*

Further information:

- Patent law is handling data on technical inventions.
- Personal data: Copyright law includes personal privacy, everybody owns his personal data and is allowed to decide on it.

Why learn about copyright?

Source: adapted from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10926852>

93

Notes:

- *There are several reasons why it is important to familiarise yourself with copyright law. Two are shown here:*
 - *1) When publishing your research data, your goal is to gain visibility and make other researchers aware of your findings.*
 - *2) If you want to reuse data generated or collected by others, you need to be aware of what you are allowed to do with it.*
- *Learning about copyright is essential for conducting research responsibly!*

Further information:

- -

What are protected works?

- UrhG §2, §4
- “Only the author’s own intellectual creations constitute works within the meaning of this act”

Literary works (written works, speeches)	Computer programms	Musical works
Pantomimic and dance work	Artistic work, including works of architecture	Cinematographic works
Photographic works	Illustrations of scientific or technical nature (maps, plans, tables)	Collections and databases

Source: https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/englisch_urhg/index.html (accessed 2025-11-03)

94

Notes:

- *The act on copyright and related rights regulates all aspects of copyright in Germany and provides a definition of the types of works protected by copyright law.*
- [Read the quote]
- *What is protected by copyright? Creative works such as musical and literary works, dance and photography, among others.*
- *What is not protected by copyright? However, facts, ideas and hard work are not!*

Further information:

- -

Copyright requirements

Individuality

Must be a personal creation or be derived from personal choices of its maker.

Originality

Must show a certain level of originality, i.e. exhibit a degree of creativity, which exceeds standard or routine effort.

Content	Individuality	Originality	Copyright protected?
Computer programs (e.g. a specific simulation)	✓	✓	✓
AI generated (e.g. ChatGPT)	✗	✗	✗
Raw data from scientific instruments	✗	✗	✗

Source: adapted from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10926852>

95

Notes:

- *In order to qualify for copyright protection, a work must demonstrate both originality and individuality.*
- [Read the definition on the slide]
- *Let us apply these requirements to three examples: 1) computer programs; 2) AI-generated content; and 3) raw data from scientific instruments.*

Further information:

- For more detailed information check the provided source.

Public domain of research results

1 “Scientific content, research results, theories, concepts, ideas, facts, formulae or findings are not licensable as such, as they are in the public domain.”

2 “They may therefore be used by anyone for any purpose.”

3 “Nobody can prohibit another person from using existing knowledge. [...] it is never possible to commit ‘theft’ of scientific content [...].”

4 “[...] scientific works only enjoy copyright protection because of their form of presentation, but not because of the ideas, findings and results they contain.”

Source: <https://doi.org/10.24921/2025.94115974> (text translated with DeepL)

96

Notes:

- *There has been a lot of discussion about whether research results should be covered by copyright or count as public domain. The following arguments are taken from the Creative Commons Public Licence Handbook, written by leading experts in copyright and science. They explain why research results are within public domain.*
- [Go through the slide step by step]

Further information:

- The points made here are very important. Make it clear to the participants that this is not up for debate. This is what experts in the field say.

There is no copyright on (unprocessed) research data!

Picture of the molecules and reaction

Tabulated properties of experimental materials

Formula	Mol mass	Mass [g]	Volume [mL]	Density [g/mL]	mmol	Equiv./yield
4-fluorobenzaldehyde (4-fluorobenzaldehyde)						
S C ₇ H ₅ FO	124	2.00	1.73	1.16	16.1	1.00
ethanamine (ethanamine in Wasser)						
R C ₂ H ₇ N	45.1	1.65	2.04	0.810	24.2	1.50
Potassium carbonate (K ₂ CO ₃)						
R C ₆ K ₂ O ₃	138	2.23	0.00	0.00	16.1	1.00
tetrabutylazanium;bromide (reactant)						
R C ₁₆ H ₃₆ BrN	322	1.56	0.00	0.00	4.83	0.300
4-(ethylamino)benzaldehyde (SG1-V2448-A)						
P C ₉ H ₁₁ NO	149	0.181	0.00	0.00	1.21	8%

Solvent(s):

Brief description of the experiment

Description:

4-Fluorobenzaldehyde (2.00 g, 1.73 mL, 16.1 mmol, 1.00 equiv), ethanamine (66% 1.09 g, 1.35 mL, 24.2 mmol, 1.50 equiv), tetrabutylazanium;bromide (1.56 g, 4.83 (0.300 equiv) and Potassium carbonate (2.23 g, 16.1 mmol, 1.00 equiv) were stirred over a period of three days. Water was given to the reaction and the resulting mixture extracted three times with ethyl acetate. The combined organic phases were washed with brine and dried over Na₂SO₄ and filtered.

Type of Purification: Flash-Chromatography

Dangerous Products:

TLC control: Rf-value: 0.67 (Solvent: cyclohexane/ethyl acetate 1:1)

Additional information for publication and purification details:

As preparation for the column chromatography (dryload), silica gel was added (6 g) and the mixture of combined organic phases + silica gel were evaporated. The obtained crude product was purified via flash-chromatography on silica gel using cyclohexane/ethyl acetate 4:1

Analysis:

¹H NMR (CHMO:0000593) | ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (1H NMR)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) [7.27 ppm], ppm] δ = 9.73 (s, 1H), 7.72–7.68 (m, 2H), 6.62–6.60 (m, 2H), 4.37 (br. s., 1H), 3.26 (q, J = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 1.30 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CHMO:0000595) | ¹³C nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (13C NMR)

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) [77.0 ppm], ppm] δ = 190.2, 153.3, 132.3 (2C), 126.4, 111.7 (2C), 37.9, 14.5.

¹H NMR (CHMO:0000630) | infrared absorption spectroscopy (IR)

IR (ATR, ν) = 3291, 2967, 2923, 2870, 2852, 2809, 2731, 1661, 1586, 1570, 1566, 1562, 1545, 1534, 1508, 1498, 1474, 1451, 1437, 1427, 1395, 1378, 1366, 1342, 1310, 1283, 1231, 1147, 1109, 1062, 1044, 997, 824, 810, 634, 619, 590, 583, 510, 426 cm⁻¹.

¹H NMR (CHMO:0000470) | mass spectrometry (MS)

EI (m/z, 70 eV, 60 °C): 149 (100), 134 (99). HRMS (C₉H₁₁ON): Calcd 149.0835, Found 149.0835.

Analysis of the measurement data

Figures: Adaptation of "Abbildungen 1", "Abbildung 2", "Abbildung 3", "Abbildung 4" by Thomas Hartmann licensed under [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) via [heiBOOKS](https://www.heibooks.de/) (adaptation: adding description and arrows)

97

Notes:

- Now, let us take a look at chemistry-specific data. A lawyer analysed a typical data publication from the Chemotion Repository in the context of copyright. What he found was as follows:
- **Pictures of molecules and reactions** are not protected by copyright because there is a standardised way of representing chemical structures in chemistry. For example, there are rules regarding bond lengths and angles. This is not a personal creation and has no originality, as it is based on a convention that everyone follows.
- **Tabulated properties** of experimental materials are not protected by copyright because this is also a standardised representation of data.
- **Brief descriptions of experiments** are not protected by copyright because they are technical descriptions of experiments. There is no creativity involved. However, if you wrote it as a poem, it might be.
- **Analysis of the measurement data** is not protected by copyright because the data was generated by the instrument, and the analysis follows community conventions.

Further information:

- In case there are any questions on that topic. A more simple example to illustrate this could be: Imagine you are measuring the outdoor temperature. In principle, anyone can take a reading at a given place and time. It is a natural phenomenon. There is no personal creativity or originality involved.

There is no copyright on (unprocessed) research data!

Picture of the molecules and reaction

Tabulated properties of experimental materials

Formula	Mol mass	Mass [g]	Volume [mL]	Density [g/mL]	mmol	Equiv	yield
4-fluorobenzaldehyde (4-fluorobenzaldehyde)	S	C ₇ H ₅ FO	124	2.00	1.73	16.1	1.00
ethanamine (ethanamine in Wasser)	R	C ₂ H ₇ N	45.1	1.65	2.04	0.34	1.50
Potassium carbonate (K ₂ CO ₃)	R	C ₂ K ₂ O ₃	138	2.23	0.00	0.00	1.00
tetrabutylazanium;bromide (reactant)	R	C ₁₆ H ₃₆ BrN	322	1.56	0.00	4.83	0.300
4-(ethylamino)benzaldehyde (SG1-V2448-A)	P	C ₉ H ₁₁ NO	149	0.181	0.00	1.21	85%

Solvent(s):

Description:

4-Fluorobenzaldehyde (2.00 g, 1.73 mL, 16.1 mmol, 1.00 equiv), ethanamine (66% in water) (1.09 g, 1.35 mL, 24.2 mmol, 1.50 equiv), tetrabutylazanium;bromide (1.56 g, 4.83 mL, 0.300 equiv) and Potassium carbonate (2.23 g, 16.1 mmol, 1.00 equiv) were stirred over a period of three days. Water was given to the reaction and the resulting mixture extracted three times with ethyl acetate. The combined organic phases were washed with brine and dried over Na₂SO₄ and filtered.

Type of Purification: Flash-Chromatography

Dangerous Products:

TLC control: Rf-value: 0.67 (Solvent: cyclohexane/ethyl acetate 1:1)

Additional information for publication and purification details:

As preparation for the column chromatography (dryload), silica gel was added (6 g) and the mixture of combined organic phases + silica gel were evaporated. The obtained crude product was purified via flash-chromatography on silica gel using cyclohexane/ethyl acetate 4:1

Analysis:

¹H NMR (CHMO:0000593) | ¹H nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (1H NMR)

¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) [7.27 ppm], ppm] δ = 9.73 (s, 1H), 7.72–7.68 (m, 2H), 6.62–6.60 (m, 2H), 4.37 (br. s., 1H), 3.26 (q, J = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 1.30 (t, J = 7.2 Hz, 3H).

¹³C NMR (CHMO:0000595) | ¹³C nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (13C NMR)

¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃) [77.0 ppm], ppm] δ = 190.2, 153.3, 132.3 (2C), 126.4, 111.7 (2C), 37.9, 14.5.

CHMO:0000630 | infrared absorption spectroscopy (IR)

IR (KBr) = 3291, 2967, 2923, 2870, 2852, 2809, 2731, 1661, 1586, 1570, 1566, 1562, 1545, 1508, 1498, 1474, 1451, 1437, 1427, 1395, 1378, 1366, 1342, 1310, 1283, 1231, 1147, 1077, 1062, 1044, 997, 824, 810, 634, 619, 590, 583, 510, 426 cm⁻¹.

CHMO:0000470 | mass spectrometry (MS)

EI (m/z, 70 eV, 60 °C): 149 (100), 134 (99). HRMS (C₉H₁₁ON): Calcd 149.0835, Found 149.0835.

Brief description of the experiment

Analysis of the measurement data

Figures: Adaptation of "Abbildungen 1", "Abbildung 2", "Abbildung 3", "Abbildung 4" by Thomas Hartmann licensed under [CC BY-SA 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) via [heiBOOKS](https://www.heibooks.org/) (adaptation: adding description and arrows)

98

Notes:

- The lawyer concluded that this dataset, published in the Chemotion Repository, is in the public domain.
- Note: This may not apply to other types of data. However, in most cases, unprocessed research data is not protected by copyright.
- This is what the lawyer found, and you can check the provided source for more information.

Further information:

- -

Copyright

In general:

- Raw research data is not protected by copyright.
- You need to check whether your data meets the requirements to be protected by copyright.
- If it is protected by copyright, then there are different author rights.

Notes:

- *Short conclusion:*
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- -

When does data protection play a role?

What kind of data is collected?

A) Data without personal reference:
Data protection is not relevant!
This is the typical case in chemistry.

A) Data with personal reference (e.g. interview, survey, video recordings, human samples):

Data protection is relevant!

Notes:

- Consider the data you work with. Do you collect data with personal reference?
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- -

What is personal data?

Legal basis:

- General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)
- German Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG)
- Data protection laws of the federal states
- Area-specific data protection law and statute law

Definition:

- Art. 4, GDPR: “any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’). An identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly”
 - e.g. name, age, address, location data, IP address
- In addition: Special categories of personal data (“sensitive” personal data)
 - e.g. racial or ethnic origin, political opinion, processing of genetic data, health data, sexual orientation

101

Notes:

- *What is data with personal reference? Take a look at the General Data Protection Regulation.*
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- German translations of the “legal basis”, in case you want to check them out yourself:
- Datenschutzgrundverordnung (DSGVO)
- Bundesdatenschutzgesetz (BDSG)
- Landesdatenschutzgesetze (e.g., Thüringer Datenschutzgesetz (ThürDSG, öffentliche Stellen wie die Uni)
- Bereichsspezifisches Datenschutzrecht (e.g., Sozialgesetzbücher, Polizeigesetz, Thüringer Hochschulgesetz)
- Satzungsrecht/Statute law (e.g., examination regulation of the university)

Processing of personal data

Processing:

- Is generally prohibited except

- a law permits it or persons give informed consent
- Take care of specific data security requirements (e.g. storage place and time, access)
- Consider technical measures like pseudonymisation, anonymisation

Data protection law relevant for doing research, also project settings can require confidentiality!

Notes:

- If you work with personal data, the following aspects are important:
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- If you know that people in the workshop work with personal data, you should consider providing additional information on anonymisation and data security, such as password-protected folders.

Self-working phase

1. Go back to your RDMO project
2. Answer the questions of your DMP in the [legal obligations and conditions](#) section

Notes:

- *No it's time for our next self-working phase. Therefore, go back to your RDMO project and answer the questions in the section on legal obligations and conditions.*
- [Leave room for solving technical problems and questions]

Further information:

- In RDMO, square checkboxes allow multiple answers to be selected, while round radio buttons allow only one choice. This visual distinction helps users clearly identify whether a question expects a decision or multiple applicable options.
- “Reuse answers” copies existing answers from another dataset.
- “Apply this answer to all tabs where this question is empty” propagates the current answer to all other datasets without a value.
- The eraser icon deletes the current dataset definition.

Discussion

What difficulties did you encounter in the self-working phase?

Do you know any other significant research codes or professional standards?

Who can help you answer any unclear questions of this section?

104

Notes:

- *Now that you have filled in the legal obligations and conditions section of your DMP, we would like to discuss your experiences and any difficulties you have encountered.*
- [Go through the guiding questions on the slide]

Further information:

- Lead the discussion by using the guiding questions on the slide.
- Motivate participants to actively take part in the discussion.
- If there is little or no feedback, ask one or two participants to present what they filled out in their DMP and whether they encountered any problems.
- If there is too much feedback within the allotted time, ask the participants to type their remaining questions in the chat (online workshop) or to save their questions for the next break (onsite workshop).

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Section 6

Responsibilities and resources

105

Notes:

- *The final section of our chemistry-specific DMP template covers responsibilities and resources. Let's dive right in!*

Further information:

- -

Section 6: Questions

Responsibilities

- Who is responsible for the appropriate handling of research data (description of roles and responsibilities within the project)?
- Who is responsible for curating the data after the project's duration?

Resources

- What resources (costs, time or other) are required to implement appropriate research data management in the project?

106

Notes:

- *The slide shows the questions that you will be answering in your DMP during the self-working phase, but first we will give you some background information on the topics involved.*
- [Go through the questions on the slide]

Further information:

- -

ORCID and ROR ID

- ORCID (Open Researcher and Contributor ID)
- Globally recognised registry for the identification and connection of researchers and their research activities
- Increasingly being used for verification purposes when registering for certain research-related tools and services
- Linking between ORCID and other author ID schemes possible
- <https://orcid.org/> - get your own ORCID!

- Research Organization Registry (ROR) - <https://ror.org/>
- Global, community-led registry of open persistent identifiers for research organisations containing associated metadata (e.g. type of organisation, website)

https://knowledgebase.nfdi4chem.de/knowledge_base/docs/pid/

107

Notes:

- *For this section, we will keep the theoretical input short. Two persistent identifiers (PIDs) that are relevant to the topic of responsibilities are ORCID and ROR.*
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- -

Cost factors

- Existing RDM expertise (personnel costs are often the biggest factor at 70% +!)
- Data volume
- Heterogeneity/complexity of data types
- Sensitive data (effort for anonymisation/pseudonymisation/obtaining consent)
- Required computing power and required data connection/interfaces
- Licence fees
- Usage and access model
- Compliance with legal obligations (e.g. acquisition of special furniture/software for data security/data protection)

OpenAIRE guide on estimating RDM costs:
<https://www.openaire.eu/rdm-costs/>

108

Notes:

- *It is rather difficult to estimate the various cost factors related to RDM. Therefore, we would like to provide you with a general overview of the factors to consider.*
- [Go through the information on the slide.]
- *To improve your ability to estimate costs, take a look at OpenAIRE's "Estimating Costs RDM Tool", which provides cost factors for the various stages of the data life cycle.*

Further information:

- -

Costs - DFG

Project-specific costs are funded:

- Preparation of research data for connection use
- Transfer of research data into existing infrastructures
- Personnel costs
- Project-specific hardware and software
- User fees (e.g. infrastructures)
- So-called INF projects in SFBs

BUT basic equipment is not funded!

109

Notes:

- *When writing your proposal and/or DMP, bear in mind that the DFG can fund project-specific RDM costs.*
- [Go through the information on the slide]
- *However, the DFG does not fund basic equipment (including replacements), as it is assumed that this is already available.*

Further information:

- 'Basic equipment' refers to the equipment typically used by a department, institute or field of work. This includes replacement purchases that are necessary. When granting funding, the DFG assumes that the standard equipment is available and does not fund such requirements as a matter of principle.

Group discussion

Breakout session

Discuss the following aspects in your group and make notes on the provided whiteboard :

- How are responsibilities managed at your site?
- Are you able to estimate the (personnel) costs and efforts for implementing appropriate research data management?

110

Notes:

- *It's time for our last group work. Therefore, please go to your group and discuss the following aspects:*
- [Go through the aspects on the slide]
- *Take some notes during your group work to present your results later on in the discussion.*

Further information:

- Group the participants in groups of 4-6 people.
- For online workshops: create breakout rooms (which you should try out prior to your workshop) and provide an online whiteboard to the participants using the tool you like. The whiteboard should contain the exercise description and enough space for notes.
- For onsite workshops: distribute the groups in the room and provide material for note taking if necessary.

Self-working phase

1. Go back to your RDMO project
2. Answer the final questions of your DMP in the **responsibilities and resources** section

Notes:

- *Let's head to our last self-working phase. Therefore, go back to your RDMO project and answer the final questions in the section on responsibilities and resources.*
- [Leave room for solving technical problems and questions]

Further information:

- In RDMO, square checkboxes allow multiple answers to be selected, while round radio buttons allow only one choice. This visual distinction helps users clearly identify whether a question expects a decision or multiple applicable options.
- “Reuse answers” copies existing answers from another dataset.
- “Apply this answer to all tabs where this question is empty” propagates the current answer to all other datasets without a value.
- The eraser icon deletes the current dataset definition.

Discussion

What difficulties did you encounter in the group work / self-working phase?

Did you find the answer options sufficient to complete the template?

Were there any similarities in your group's answers to the questions?

112

Notes:

- *Now that you have filled in the responsibilities and resources section of your DMP, we would like to discuss your experiences and any difficulties you have encountered.*
- [Go through the guiding questions on the slide]

Further information:

- Lead the discussion by using the guiding questions on the slide.
- Motivate participants to actively take part in the discussion.
- If there is little or no feedback, ask one or two participants to present what they filled out in their DMP and whether they encountered any problems.
- If there is too much feedback within the allotted time, ask the participants to type their remaining questions in the chat (online workshop) or to save their questions for the next break (onsite workshop).

RDMO

Additional functionalities

113

Notes:

- *Congratulations! You have successfully created your first DMP in RDMO.*
- *Now, we would like to show you some additional software features that will make your DMP work easier.*
- [Head to the RDMO instance used for the workshop (e.g. <https://rdmo.nfdi4chem.de/>) and demonstrate some of the possibilities mentioned below while using the software.]

Further information:

- Export function: Show the export of a DMP and the possible export formats (e.g., .pdf, .rtf, .md,... vs .xml, .csv, .json).
- Import function: Show the import of values into a DMP from a .xml file.
- Snapshots: Show how to create intermediate versions of a DMP, known as “snapshots”.
- Collaborative work: Show how to share a DMP by adding members to the project.

Q&A Session

What questions do you have?

Notes:

- *We have now complete the chemistry-specific DMP template in RDMO. What questions do you still have?*
- [Wait at least 45-60 seconds for questions to come up]

Further information:

- Lead the discussion and motivate participants to actively take part in the Q&A.
- If there is little or no feedback, ask one or two participants specifically if questions that they asked earlier on were answered/are clearer by now.
- If there is too much feedback within the allotted time, ask the participants to type their remaining questions in the chat or to save their questions for the follow-up Q&A session.

„Homework“ and follow-up Q&A session

- Optional homework:

You filled in the DMP template for one dataset during the workshop. Complete your DMP for your whole project in the upcoming weeks.

- Follow-up Q&A session:

Any questions left or new ones arising during the homework? Join our **follow-up Q&A session on XX.XX., XX-XX am/pm** (invitation follows).

115

Notes:

- *You completed your DMP for one dataset during this workshop.*
- *We would like to propose a voluntary homework until the follow-up Q&A session:*
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- Plan a follow-up Q&A session that takes place approximately two weeks after the workshop. Participants can use this time to complete their DMP and compile any remaining questions.

Wrap-up

NFDI4Chem service portfolio

116

Notes:

- *Last but not least, we would like to briefly introduce the NFDI4Chem services.*

Further information:

- -

All chemists publish FAIR data

That is our vision. To get there, we will support scientists in their efforts to collect, store, process, analyse, publish and re-use research data in chemistry. NFDI4Chem develops and maintains a national research data infrastructure for the research domain of chemistry in Germany, and we enable innovative services and science based on research data.

NFDI4Chem is a DFG-funded non-commercial consortium from the community for the community.

Visit our website:

<https://www.nfdi4chem.de/>

What can we do for you?

Click on a category below to find out more about our work!

Electronic Lab Notebooks

Chemistry Repositories

Knowledge Base

Terminology Service

Helpdesk

Search Service

Notes:

- The central access point to services from, as well as information about the NFDI4Chem is our webpage. There you can find information about our goals, governance, links to useful material collections, and all our services. You can also find the latest news and events.

Further information:

- -

Contact & Helpdesk

Looking for contact information or help on research data management, data repositories or electronic lab notebooks (ELN) for chemistry?

Get in touch with us!

Task Area	Lead	Project Manager
1 Management	Christoph Steinbeck	Franziska Eberl
2 Smart Lab	Nicole Jung	Adam Basha
3 Repositories	Felix Bach & Matthias Razum	Christian Bonatto Minella
4 Standards	Steffen Neumann	N.N.
5 Community & Training	Sonja Herres-Pawlis & Johannes Liermann	Jochen Ortmeyer
6 Synergies	Oliver Koepfer	Johannes Hunold

Helpdesk

Contact our consortium-wide Helpdesk to get advice and support on most topics related to research data management, data repositories or electronic lab notebooks (ELN) for chemistry.

Send an email to helpdesk@nfdi4chem.de

Single point of entry to support you with all questions you may have regarding research data management.

For example:

- Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs)
- Data Management Plans (DMPs)
- FAIR Data

helpdesk@nfdi4chem.de

Notes:

- *The helpdesk of NFDI4Chem is there for all your questions around the broader topic of research data management in chemistry. Whether you need specific information and help for a project or have more general questions. Contact us any time, even if you are not sure if it is a question for NFDI4Chem.*
- *Expert from different fields are part of the helpdesk team from electronic lab notebooks, to data management plans to standardisation and FAIR data in general.*

Further information:

- -

Selection of other services by NFDI4Chem

NFDI4Chem Stammtisch

interactive, insightful
& up-to-date

Social Media

informative, engaging
& connected

Knowledge Base

comprehensive, reliable
& chemistry-specific

Terminology Service

interoperable, controlled
& ensures consistency

Repositories

FAIR, discipline-specific
& open

Dataset Search Service

efficient, focused
& easy-to-use

and much more ...
www.nfdi4chem.de

119

Notes:

- NFDI4Chem offers a number of services for you as a researcher, here are some examples:
- [Go through the information on the slide]
- Make sure to stay in contact and follow us on social media and join our monthly NFDI4Chem Stammtisch where experts show latest developments and use cases.

Further information:

- -

Evaluation

Notes:

- *Your feedback is important to us.*

Further information:

- Make sure to give the participants some time to fill out the evaluation directly after/during the workshop. Otherwise many people will forget.

Thank you for participating in the evaluation!

QR code

[Link to the evaluation](#)

121

Notes:

- *Your feedback is important to us.*
- *Please take a few minutes to fill in the evaluation of today's workshop. Thanks a lot!*

Further information:

- Provide link to your evaluation as well as a QR code on this slide.

Acknowledgement

This workshop is inspired by the materials of

- Train-the-Trainer Concept on Research Data Management
(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4071471> / <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5773203>)
- Research Data Management Team Friedrich Schiller University Jena
- Research Data Management Team RWTH Aachen University
- TU9 German Universities of Technology
(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3466206>)

Notes:

- *In the end, we would like to acknowledge some materials that were used to conceptualise this workshop and weren't mentioned on any other slides yet.*
- [Go through the information on the slide]

Further information:

- -

How to cite this workshop?

Please quote as follows:

NFDI4Chem (2026)“DMP Writing Made Easy: A Hands-on Workshop for Chemists”.

Licence: [CC0 1.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

(unless stated otherwise on specific slides)

Notes:

- *You are welcome to reuse our workshop materials for your own purposes.*
- *Unless stated otherwise for specific elements on specific slides, the workshop material is licensed under a Creative Commons CC0 1.0 licence (public domain).*
- *As part of good research practice, we kindly ask that you cite our workshop materials.*

Further information:

- -

NFDI₄Chem

ENHANCE
YOUR
DATA.

Thank you for your attention!

124

Notes:

- *Thank you for your attention, actively participating in our workshop and your valuable feedback!*
- *We wish you a lovely remaining day and hope to see you at our follow-up Q&A session!*

Further information:

- -